

DEVELOPMENT OF AN ON-LINE ANALYSIS METHOD FOR THE THERMOPLASTIC IMPREGNATION PROCESS

M. Christmann*, P. Mitschang, L. Medina

Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH, Kaiserslautern, Germany

* Corresponding author (marcel.christmann@ivw.uni-kl.de)

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1 Introduction

Due to their specific properties such as high toughness, chemical resistance, or unlimited shelf life, the demand for continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic polymer composites has steadily increased over the past years. This group of materials is used in a wide range of applications, e.g. in the aerospace or transportation industry. In order to improve the processes, enormous efforts have been made to examine the effects during the impregnation as well as to model the impregnation process [1-5]. But presently, there are no possibilities available which enable the online observation of occurring effects. Thus, all effects are investigated in retrospect by e.g. polished cross sections or by CT scans.

The paper gives some insights into the development of a transparent tool for fiber reinforced thermoplastics, which enables the online observation of the impregnation process by high resolution movies. Thereby, this development will be the basis for faster analysis of occurring effects as well as for a systematic process optimization.

2 Tool Development for Visible Observation

In the past, major scientific findings have been made by the analysis of the injection process for thermoset resins using transparent tools. These findings have made an important contribution to prove the theoretical considerations about the injection process and they have been used for the further development of simulation tools to predict the resin flow front. But in contrast to the processing of fiber reinforced thermosets, the necessary temperature and pressure is much higher for thermoplastic matrix materials. Thus, there are significant differences between the tool designs for the different matrix types. In order to enable the visual observation of the impregnation

process, there are two major aspects which have to be considered. On the one hand, it is necessary to develop a tool which offers a sufficient transparency to the in-plane direction of the laminate, which enables the integration of a camera system and also withstands the applied pressure and temperature. On the other hand, a proper fiber-matrix combination is necessary to make effects visible which occur inside the laminate, respectively inside the rovings.

At the beginning of the development, some basic boundary conditions for the optical observation affecting the tool design had to be set. It should be possible to make effects visible, which occur on the surface of the laminate as well as inside the laminate. Thus, top and bottom lighting of the samples had to be integrated. Thereby, it had to be possible to regulate the brightness for both lighting units individually and infinitely, because the reflection of the laminate as well as the light transmission varies during the impregnation process and is different for every material combination. Furthermore, different requirements had to be fulfilled to the camera system:

- Different degrees of magnifications should be adjustable.
- The focus point has to be fixed during the pressing cycle, although the tool is moving.
- The camera system has to be protected against thermal radiation of the tool.

In order to meet these requirements, the camera system was mounted at a right angle sideways at the upper tool (see Figure 1). The view inside the tool is enabled by a mirror arranged in 45° about the upper tool. This allows to easily variegate the distance between camera and laminate, respectively to change the magnification easily. Furthermore, due to this adjustment, the focus point is set constant to the

surface of the sample, the camera is protected from thermal radiation and the tool height is reduced. The lighting of the sample from top is done by a LED ring, which surrounds the lens of the camera and thus illuminates the sample in the same direction like camera view.

Considering the demands on the tool, different materials have been taken into account. Due to the high process temperatures and the risk for a thermal shock, NEOCERAM N-11 has been chosen as transparent material. The biggest advantage is its low thermal expansion coefficient of $1.2 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, which leads to a thermal shock resistance of up to 600 K. In contrast, the thermal conductivity of $1.79 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}$ is relatively low compared to steel ($40 \text{ W/m} \cdot \text{K}$). This makes it more difficult to heat and cool the tool. Additionally, there is only reduced space for the integration of heating and cooling channels due to the glass elements. Finally, the heating is realized by electric cartridge heaters and the cooling is done by water. The final design of the tool is given in Figure 2.

The lower lighting system is integrated into an aluminum cage, which is thermally separated from the carrier plate by a ceramic insulation plate. High power LEDs have been chosen as light source for the upper as well as for the lower illumination. They offer the advantage of small dimension and high light intensity. Beyond, the color of the LEDs can be changed in any order. The carrier plate is made of tooling steel and offers two stiffeners in form of a cross in the center below the glass inserts, which reduce the mechanical load on the glass. Furthermore, the heat transfer into the glass is improved by increasing the contact area. The base plate carries the glass insert of the lower tool part and the cooling channels for the water cooling. The cartridge heaters are installed into the overlying shearing edge plate.

The upper part of the tool comprises 4 components. The drawing case takes the mirror for the deflection of the camera pictures. Furthermore, it transfers the force of an external pressing equipment to the cavity in order to generate the impregnation pressure. Again, a ceramic insulation plate takes care for the thermal separation between the drawing case and the upper carrier plate. The stamp consists of a steel frame which carries the upper glass insert. While the

stamp is dipped into the shearing edge plate, there is a heat transfer into the stamp due to the minimum distance between the two parts. This is of major importance, because no heating elements are integrated into the upper tool. Once more, the mechanical forces on the glass inserts are reduced due to the use of a supporting carrier plate. The carrier plate and the stamp including the glass insert are shown in Figure 3.

Looking through the glass, which is glued into the stamp with an elastic, high temperature resistant adhesive, the stiffening elements can be seen. Due to the modular design of the tool, the stamp can easily be changed in order to carry out different experiments. The test equipment, which is mounted on the pressing unit, is shown in Figure 4. The technical specifications of the tool are given below:

- Sample size: 60x60 mm
- Cavity height: 15 mm
- Temperature: 20 – 280 °C (68 – 536 °F)
- Heating rate: 10 K/min
- Cooling rate: 10 K/min
- Pressure: 0 – 20 bar (0 – 2 MPa)

For the capturing of the movie, two different cameras of Allied Vision Technologies have been used. A digital video camera (type: Marlin) and a monochrome video camera (type: Stingray) has been selected.

3 Examination of Impregnation Process

3.1 Materials in Use

For the examination of the impregnation progress, a glass fiber textile of Hexcel (typ: 1038) has been chosen as reinforcement material. It is a balanced textile with a twill 2/2 weaving pattern and a weight per area of 600 g/m^2 . Glass fibers rovings offer the big advantage to become transparent when they are fully impregnated. Remaining voids inside the textile become visible. Principally, thermoplastic polymers with an amorphous structure should be preferred due to the advantage of transparency in liquid as well as in solid state. But a requirement for transparency of a composite is that the refractive index n of the two materials is equal to each other. If the refractive index is different, the incoming light is

refracted, one part is going through the material and the other part is reflected (see Figure 5). Thereby, the reflected light is the reason, why an object can be seen. In case of a fiber reinforced material such objects can be fibers or entrapped air. If the fibers and the matrix therefore have an equal refractive index, only the entrapped air becomes visible.

From literature it is known that glass fibers have a refractive index of $n = 1.55$, which is comparable to epoxy resin ($n = 1.55$ to $n = 1.60$) [6, 7]. Thus, a semi-crystalline Polypropylene (PP) and a Polyamide 12 (PA12) has been selected. The refractive index of PP is $n = 1.49$ and $n = 1.52$ for PA12. Both values are given for the solid state [7, 8]. In comparison, air has a refractive index of $n \approx 1$ [9]. Some general information about the matrix materials are given in Table 1.

3.2 Optimization of the Equipment due to Pretrials

Due to the fact that the cartridge heaters are only integrated into the lower tool, there could be a temperature difference between the upper and the lower tool. Thus, before carrying out the first impregnation trials, the temperature difference was checked. Therefore, the tool temperature was set to $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($= 392\text{ }^{\circ}\text{F}$). After keeping the temperature constant for 10 minutes in order to enable a homogenization, a difference of 20 K at the outside of the glass inserts was recognized ($190\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the lower tool and $170\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the upper tool). Thus, in order to fully melt the polymer, it was decided to carry out the impregnation trials with a set temperature of $240\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($= 464\text{ }^{\circ}\text{F}$) for both matrix materials. The PP matrix material was used for the first impregnation trials. One layer of textile has been placed on top and bottom of four PP film layers. The tool was preheated to the set process temperature. Then the material was placed inside the tool, the tool was closed and a pressure of 10 bar ($= 1\text{ MPa}$) was applied for 2,000 seconds. Subsequently, the tool was cooled to $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in order to remove the sample.

At a first stage only lighting from the bottom was used, whereby the video camera system has been mounted. Because the used LEDs can change the color in any order, this enables to find settings, which are leading to the best results for the

observation of the impregnation process regarding image quality, image contrast and light refraction.

The pictures taken with different lighting colors at the beginning of the impregnation process show, that there are significant differences (see Figure 6). The color settings have been made for the three basic colors and for white light. When using the blue light, the picture offers a low brightness and the areas between the rovings of the textile seem to be very small. The brightness of the red illuminated sample is much higher, but the image contrast is poor, so that the edges of the fibers become blurred. Compared to this, the picture with green lighting offers a pretty high image contrast. Finally, the white lighting shows the best image quality. The macro voids between the rovings can be seen as well as different intensities of light transmission through the fiber bundles.

In a further stage pretrials have been carried out using the lighting system from the top only. Again four layers of PP and two layers of glass textile have been used. But this configuration did not lead to useful results (see Figure 7). The pictures showed many overexposed areas all over the sample, which are caused by reflections at the sample, at the ceramic glass and as well at the mirror. Furthermore, the focal point could not be adjusted well and the sample was displayed with wrong colors (pictures are greenish).

As reason for the wrong colors, the LED lighting system itself in combination with the used camera system was identified. The light of white color LEDs does only contain a small spectrum range of each three basic colors. Furthermore, the camera has a different sensitivity for the light spectrum. Thus, the pictures are displayed with wrong colors. Afterwards, several modifications and optimizations at the lighting system have been carried out. The position of the LEDs has been changed in order to reduce the reflections. Furthermore, the spectrum of the LED light was changed and the monochrome camera was used. Finally, the matrix material was changed, because the refractive index of solid PA12 is more similarly to glass fibers. Two layers of glass textile have been combined with 12 layers of PA12 film in order to get the same thickness of the laminate.

Due to these optimizations, the overexposed areas and the wrong colors could be eliminated. Beyond,

the focus as well as the depth of focus could be improved. Since these results, all following investigations were carried out with PA12.

3.3 Process Analysis by Observation

For the observation of the impregnation process using top lighting, the image section was reduced so that a high magnification could be realized. During the examination, different effects became obvious (see Figure 8). The picture taken after 3 seconds shows the textile after starting the process. After the tool is closed and the process pressure P_p is applied to the laminate, the reinforcing textile is compacted. This compaction depends on the closing speed of the press and is done within approximately one second after the upper tool has touched the textile (picture taken after 6 and 7 seconds).

After compaction, the impregnation process is divided into the macro- and the micro-impregnation as it is affirmed by many investigations done in the past [10,11]. First, the intersections of the weft and warp yarns were filled with polymer. The flow front is marked with a white line in the pictures. The macro-impregnation is completed very fast within a split of seconds (see Figure 9).

Subsequently, the micro impregnation process of the rovings can be observed (see Figure 10). The rovings are penetrated with polymer circularly in the in-plane direction at each fiber bundle crossing point of the textile (not impregnated areas are exemplary marked for some rovings with a white line). It is important to note, that there is no difference in the impregnation behavior between the warp and weft rovings for this balanced textile. The difference in appearance is a result of the exposure of light. Furthermore, during the process another effect becomes obvious, which is described theoretically in the literature [12]. In some areas, the polymer penetrates the rovings parallel to the filament direction. This effect occurs much faster than the rest of the impregnation and is commonly known as fingering.

The following examination of the impregnation process was carried out using illumination of the sample from the bottom. Therefore, it was decided to reduce the magnification in order to observe a bigger image section. Thus, the video recordings give a good overview on the whole impregnation

process of the laminate. After running the process for 225 seconds, the macro impregnation is completed for a long time and the gaps between the rovings can be clearly seen (see Figure 11). Subsequently, the penetration of the rovings is in progress, which is leading to a larger transparent area between the rovings (see Figure 11; Time: 345s)

After 465 seconds of process time, the impregnation is more advanced and only the center of the roving is not yet impregnated with polymer (see Figure 12). Thereby, it is interesting to see, that the progress in impregnation is not homogeneous, i.e. some rovings are better impregnated than others. Furthermore, when comparing the overall quality, the impregnation seems to be better to the edges than in the center. Thus, it can be concluded that the displacement of entrapped air is strongly influenced by the tool dimension. Finally (465 seconds), the impregnation process seems to be completed, because no dark areas are remaining and the transmission of light has reached its maximum. Anyways, the laminate does not reach full transparency, which can be traced back to unequal refractive indices of fibers and polymer.

3.4 Examination of imaging results and real impregnation quality.

The visible observation of the impregnation process holds the potential to get information about process improvements quite easy and fast. But this is only possible, if there is a reliable correlation between the voids which are visible on the pictures and the voids, which remain in the laminate. In order to verify this correlation, laminates have been processed with different impregnation times of 5, 7, 9, and 16 minutes in order to offer different states of impregnation. Once again, the process temperature and the process pressure have been set to 240 °C (= 464°F) and 10 bar (= 1 MPa). After processing the laminates, samples have been taken of characteristic areas with respect to the taken movies. Figure 13 shows the recorded state of impregnation for the four samples before the polymer gets solid.

In order to evaluate the actual void content inside the laminate, micrographs have been taken of the samples (see Figure 14). Thereby, the samples that have been impregnated for 5, 7, and 9 minutes, have not been embedded into resin. Due to the poor

impregnation state the voids would have been completely filled with embedding resin. The pictures have been taken with a stereomicroscope. In contrast, the fully impregnated samples could be embedded into resin and the pictures have been taken with a reflecting microscope.

Overall, the analyses of the micrographs show a good correlation to the corresponding pictures taken during the impregnation process. For the samples with 5 minutes impregnation time, the roving is only impregnated at the border area. In contrast, the voids of the 7 minute sample are more concentrated in the center of the roving. This is in good accordance with the picture take of the movie whereas the rovings offer a higher brightness and the “gaps” between the rovings are bigger than at the 5 minutes picture. After 9 minutes of impregnation time the voids have further decreased. Additionally, the picture taken of the movie as well as the picture taken of the polished cross section doesn't show a continuous void formation inside the roving. Finally, the pictures taken of the sample after impregnating for 16 minutes doesn't show any remaining voids. Thus, it seems that there is a good correlation between both analysis methods.

4 Summary and Conclusion

During this research work, a method for the observation of the impregnation process of thermoplastics fiber reinforced composites was successfully developed. The new measurement tool is able to observe impregnation effects occurring on the outer layers of the laminate for the macro- and micro-impregnation. Furthermore, it was shown that it is possible to show the displacement of entrapped air and to predict the point in time when full impregnation is reached. Thereby, it could be proved that the voids, which are visible at the on-line image of the camera, are in good correlation to the voids which can be found at micrographs. Thus, this technology enables the just-in-time analysis of process or material improvements. In the future, further improvements regarding the resolution and magnification of the movies have to be realized. Additionally, a better fiber-matrix combination needs to be evaluated in order to improve the transparency of the processed laminate.

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Fig. 1: Principle arrangement of the lighting systems of the tool

Fig. 2: Main parts of the pressing tool

Fig. 3: Upper tool stamp with glass insert

Fig. 4: Mounted tool on the pressing unit

Fig. 5: Refraction of light at the fiber-matrix interface

Table 1: Properties of the used matrix material

Material	T_m	Film thickness
PP	164 °C (\approx 327 °F)	300 μ m
PA12	178 °C (\approx 352 °F)	75 μ m

Fig. 6: Different colors of bottom sample illumination

Fig. 7: Reinforcing textile inside the tool

Fig. 8: Textile compaction inside the tool

Fig. 9: Observation of macro-impregnation using top-sample illumination

Fig. 10: Effects during the micro impregnation

Fig. 11: View on the impregnation process with bottom sample illumination

Fig. 12: View on the impregnation process with bottom sample illumination

Fig. 13: Evaluation of impregnation progress for different states of impregnation

T_{imp}: 5 minutes (stereomicroscope)

T_{imp}: 7 minutes (stereomicroscope)

T_{imp}: 9 minutes (stereomicroscope)

T_{imp}: 16 minutes (reflected light microscope)

Fig. 14: Analysis of impregnation quality due to micrographs